

Potential impacts, adaptation and vulnerability of fisheries to climate change: An Indian perspective

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ABSTRACT

Climate change is one of the most important environmental challenges not only for India but also for other many countries impacting severely in various aspects of fisheries. Nearly 700 million rural populations of India directly depend on climate-sensitive sectors (agriculture, forests and fisheries) and natural resources (such as freshwater, mangroves, coastal zones, grasslands and biodiversity) for their subsistence and livelihoods. This paper reviews existing knowledge with regard to the exposure of inland fisheries to climatic changes in India. Therefore, the paper discussed the development of vulnerability index for assessing climate vulnerability of inland fisheries and, the possible adaptation measures to combat these changes by the fisheries sector. Finally we identify major gaps in knowledge that needs to be bridged to allow effective management of inland fisheries towards the challenge of climate variability in the future.

1. Introduction

Climate change is at present one of the most important environmental challenges for India. Nearly 700 million rural populations of India directly depend on climate-sensitive sectors (agriculture, forests and fisheries) and natural resources (such as freshwater, mangroves, coastal zones, grasslands and biodiversity) for their subsistence and livelihoods. Any adverse impact on water availability due to recession of glaciers, decrease in rainfall and increased flooding in certain areas would threaten food security, cause further degradation of natural ecosystems and its resident species that sustain the livelihood of rural households. India's diverse fresh water resources viz., rivers, lakes, reservoirs and associated waters the habitat for a rich diversity of aquatic organisms are threatened by climate change. The Gangetic river system, India's largest, harbours about 265 species of freshwater fish and supports a complex mix of artisanal, subsistence, traditional and semi-intensive culture fisheries based on the main river and adjoining water bodies of the Gangetic plains situated mainly in the three Indian

states of Uttar Pradesh, Bihar and West Bengal (Vass et al. 2009).

Given likely climate warming scenarios, water problems in the Ganga river basin will increase and may be critical in terms of the ecosystem goods and services derived from the inland water bodies via fisheries. Balancing the needs of the aquatic environment and other users may become difficult in many of India's aquatic ecosystems as population and associated demands increase (Das 2009).

India is the second largest producer of fish contributing 5.43% to the global fish production. The total fish production in India is 9.5 million tonnes with a contribution of 6.1 and 3.4 million tonnes from inland and marine fisheries sectors, respectively. The value of fish and fish products exported during 2013-14 was approximately Rs.30213 crores. The sector provides livelihood for 14.49 million people in the country (DAHDF 2014). But in recent years, climate variability manifested by rise of sea level, increased incidence of flood, drought, tropical cyclones and increasing

water stress in various countries of the world have adversely affected the aquatic ecosystems, fisheries and fishers' livelihood (Badjeck et al. 2010; Cruz et al. 2007; Das et al. 2013; Das et al. 2016). The multiple benefits that fisheries and aquaculture provide for alleviation of poverty are threatened by climate change.

This paper reviews existing knowledge with regard to the exposure of inland fisheries to climatic changes in India. Impacts include alterations of the climate variables, air and water temperature related to inland fisheries analysed for the last three decades and of the extreme events like drought and cyclones in the Ganga river basin. It also includes effects on distribution, breeding, bio-diversity, productivity of fishery resources and the physiological impact on fish. We then discuss the development of vulnerability index for assessing climate vulnerability of inland fisheries and, the possible adaptation measures to combat these changes by the fisheries sector. Finally we identify major gaps in knowledge that needs to be bridged to allow effective management of inland fisheries towards the challenge of climate variability in the future.

2. Climate change predictions that would potentially impact fisheries

Changes in the climate of the earth have become evident both on global and regional scales in the past few decades. The IPCC (2014) climate projections related to the fisheries sector in general indicate i) Rise in sea level could flood millions of people living in low lying areas of south, southeast and east Asia such as Vietnam, Bangladesh, India and China ii) Increase in tropical cyclones resulting in likely increase in hurricane related losses iii) Increasing salinity of ground water as well as surface water resources especially along the coast of India, China and Bangladesh and iv) an expansion of areas under water stress. Changes in India's climate have been summarized (Anonymous 2004) and some of the changes relevant to inland fisheries are: (i) an increase of 0.4° C in surface air temperatures over the past century at the national level; (ii) a trend of increasing monsoon seasonal rainfall along the west coast, in the northern state of Andhra Pradesh, and in north-western India (+10% to +12% of the normal over the last 100 years) matched with a trend of decreasing monsoon seasonal rainfall over eastern parts of the state of Madhya Pradesh, north-eastern India, and some parts of Gujarat and Kerala states (-6% to -8% of the normal over the last 100 years; (iii) a trend of multi-decadal periods of more frequent droughts, followed by less severe droughts and an overall increasing trend in severe storm incidence especially along the coast of the states of Gujarat and West Bengal at the rate of 0.011 events per year and a rising trend in the frequency of heavy rain events; (iv) indications of recession in some of the Himalayan glaciers. The Himalayas possess one of the largest resources of snow and ice and its glaciers form a source of water for the perennial rivers such as the Indus, the Ganga, and the Brahmaputra. Glacial melt may impact their long-term lean-season flows, with adverse impacts on the economy in terms of water availability and hydropower generation. The available monitoring data on Himalayan glaciers indicates that while recession of some

glaciers has occurred in some Himalayan regions in recent years, the trend is not consistent across the entire mountain chain. It is accordingly, too early to establish long-term trends, or their causation, in respect of which there are several hypotheses. (v) A rise in sea level between 1.06-1.75 mm per year consistent with 1-2 mm per year global sea level rise estimates of IPCC. The historic sea level rise for Cochin (southwest coast of India) is estimated to have been 2 cm in the last one century. An increase in mean sea level will affect waves, currents and bottom pressure in the near shore region. In general, an increase in mean water depth will be accompanied by an increase in mean wave height, resulting in a more severe wave attack on the coast and a greater wave induced littoral drift. The erosion due to sea level rise for the region is estimated to be 7125 m³ per year, implying an erosion rate of 0.3 x 10⁶ m³ per year, which could be attributed to the effects of wave attack. Using the extreme conditions of wave height and sea level rise, future erosion potential is expected to increase by 15.3% by the year 2100. Besides destruction through increased rates of erosion, the sea level rise situations also increase the risk of flooding. This will damage or destroy many coastal ecosystems such as mangroves and salt marshes, which are essential for maintaining many wild fish stocks, as well as supplying seed to aquaculture. Higher sea levels may make groundwater more saline, harming freshwater fisheries, aquaculture and agriculture and limiting industrial and domestic water uses (Vivekanandan et al. 2010).

3. Impact on fish habitat

Unlike the terrestrial environment where the impact of climate change is mainly felt directly by the agricultural crops or livestock, the impact on fisheries and aquaculture is mediated through the aquatic environment which serve as the habitat for fish. The main elements of climate change has the potential to alter the aquatic habitat characteristics impeding fish production.

It is therefore imperative to have an understanding of the specific alteration in the inland aquatic habitat quality occurring over the years due to climate change to warrant concern about the health of the inland aquatic ecosystems in general and fisheries in particular. Researchers conducted in India analysing time series data of some climate variables relevant to aquatic ecosystems and fisheries in the river Ganga and the static water ponds in West Bengal and Orissa reveal perceptible habitat quality alterations and their potential effect on fish health. These are depicted below.

3.1 Rivers

The major river systems of India which will be impacted in a climate alteration scenario are the Himalayan glacier-supported, mighty, perennial rivers such as Indus, Ganga and Brahmaputra. About 75% of discharges in Himalayan rivers occur during May-September. Similarly other major rivers which are not snow fed arising in the mid Deccan plateau of India like the Narmada, Mahi, Tapi, Godavari and Mahanadi shall have either acute or regular water shortage or face excessive flood condition as in Mahanadi (Ministry of Environment and Forest 2004).

Climate Change and Water Availability: Projections of water balance components for the 12 river basins (Ministry of Environment and Forest 2004) compare water balance components expressed as percentage of rainfall for both a control and climate change scenarios. The control is based on the daily weather generated by Ha D RM2 control climate scenarios (1981-2000). The model was run using climate scenarios for the period 2041-2060. It is observed that the impacts are different in different catchments. The increase in rainfall due to climate change does not result in an increase in the surface run-off as may be generally expected. For example, in the case of the Cauvery river basin, an increase of 2.7 per cent has been projected in the rainfall, but the run-off is projected to reduce by about 2 per cent and the evapotranspiration to increase by about 2 per cent. It may be observed that even though an increase in precipitation is projected for the Mahanadi, Brahmani, Ganga, Godavari, and Cauvery basins for the Climate Change Scenario, the corresponding total run-off for all these basins has not necessarily increased. The Sabarmati and Luni basins are likely to experience a decrease in precipitation and consequent decrease of total run-off to the tune of two-thirds of the prevailing run-off. This may lead to severe drought conditions under a future climate change scenario.

The amount of water rivers carried, is determined by precipitation, snowmelt as well as the factors that determine runoff, infiltration and evaporation in their catchments. Therefore the physical structure of a river and the capacity to maintaining in-stream habitats for fish and associated fauna and flora is flow dependent. Alteration in flow characteristics of a river will bring about changes in habitat complexity and the diversity of plants and animals and directly affects many life cycle stages of fish.

3.2 Wetlands

India has a wealth of wetland ecosystems distributed in different geographical regions. Most of the wetlands in India are directly or indirectly linked with major river systems such as the Ganges, Cauvery, Krishna, Godavari and Tapti. These ecosystems are often highly productive and harbour a unique assemblage of aquatic and terrestrial biodiversity and also provide a wide array of ecosystem goods and services. The multiple services provided by wetlands include irrigation, domestic water supply, freshwater fisheries and water for recreation. They are also playing important role in groundwater recharge, flood control, carbon sequestration and pollution abatement. However, inland and coastal wetlands are being lost and degraded faster than any other ecosystem type in the world. This trend will considerably magnify in coming years and the degradation will be exacerbated by climate changes. Climate dependency of wetlands in India is evident. Monsoonal variations has a great influence on the water spread, turbidity and aquatic vegetation of the wetlands. This is evident by the reduction in the water spread of wetlands from post –monsoon (77%) to pre-monsoon (39%) and aquatic vegetation from pre-monsoon (145%) to post –monsoon (9%) (Panigrahy et al. 2012)

As per the estimations, carbon sequestration potential of restored wetlands (over 50 year period) comes out to be about 0.4 tonnes C/ha/year. Coastal wetlands in India

especially the mangrove wetlands in eastern region and west coast serve as carbon sink sequestering approximately 1.5 metric tonne of carbon per hectare per year, and the upper layers of mangrove sediments have high carbon content, with conservative estimates indicating the levels of 10% (Kathiresan and Thakur 2008).

The wetlands are known for their rich biodiversity reserves in the form of wildlife, plants and animals but presently this significant characteristic is losing grounds at an alarming pace. Fisheries and aquaculture is a high priority area of economic gain and rural livelihood upliftment.

Hydrological processes in the watershed, and the rate of downstream discharge, determine the depth, duration and frequency of inundation of the floodplain, which periodically becomes a part of the river. Thus the river flows determine the nature and strength of a river's interaction with its floodplain, and consequently the diversity of habitats and biotic communities. Any human activity that directly or indirectly impinges upon the flows has an impact on the fishery resources.

3.3 Indian ocean

The world's oceans are affected by changes in precipitation, wind and currents as the result of geographical differences in temperature and humidity of the atmosphere. Thus, important oceanic weather systems such as the El Niño Southern Oscillation (ENSO) and the Indian Ocean monsoon will be affected by global warming.

It has been found that the sea surface temperature has increased in the Indian sea, by 0.2°C along the northwest (NW), southwest (SW) and northeast (NE) coasts, and by 0.3°C along the southeast (SE) coast during the 45 year period from 1961 to 2005. It has been predicted that the annual average sea surface temperature in the Indian seas would increase by 2.0°C to 3.5°C by 2099.

The impact of global warming on the Arabian Sea is the disruption of the natural decadal cycle in the SST after 1995, followed by a secular increase in temperature. This increase in temperature is associated with a 5-fold increase in the development of most intense cyclones (> 100 kmph) in the Arabian Sea (May-June) after 1995 (1995-2007), compared to the previous 25 years (1970-1994). (Vivekanandan et al. 2010).

3.4 Alteration of aquatic habitat quality during extreme events

3.4.1 Impact on static water ponds habitat during drought

Analysis of the rainfall data (IIMT Pune 2005) of some drought prone districts of West Bengal, India for the period 1999-2009 indicated that during the drought year 2009 the amount of rainfall during the fish breeding months (March to September) was deficient by 29% and 27% respectively during 2009 in comparison to the time period 1999-2008. The mean minimum water temperature during 1999-2009 increased by 0.46 to 0.55 °C during January – April and by 0.39 to 1.4 °C during May – September (Das et al. 2011).

Fig. 1 Averages rainfall distribution during 1999-08 compare with 2009 for deficit in rainfall of Bankura and North 24 Paraganas districts of West Bengal (Reproduced from Das et al. 2013)

3.4.2 Coastal aquatic habitat changes during storms and cyclones

Tropical cyclones are major hazards in tropical coastal regions, both in terms of loss of life and economic damage. Such cyclones originate in the Bay of Bengal during the spring (April-May) and fall (October- November) inter-monsoon. They are predicted to increase in frequency.

These cyclones with tremendous speed hit the coastline and inundate the shores with strong tidal waves severely destroying and disturbing coastal resources. The intrusion of seawater into the upstream riverine zone through estuaries, creeks and inlets has high probability to alter the chemical composition of the inland waters.

Climatic change has resulted in increased frequency of cyclones which inundate the shores. The intrusion of seawater into the upstream riverine zone through estuaries, creeks and inlets has high probability to alter the chemical composition of the inland waters. Investigations conducted in the water areas of South 24 Parganas during the occurrence of cyclone Aila in May 2009.reveal that the average water salinity in the rivers Hooghly and Matla increased from 12 to 17 ppt and in the inland confined water from 8 to 23 ppt. As a result agriculture and aquaculture activities were disrupted. (Das and Sharma 2010; CIFRI/NPCC Annual Reports 2005-2011).

4. Impact on fish population

4.1 Breeding and recruitment of fish in river Ganga

Majority of fishes of the Ganga river system breed during the monsoon months i.e. June to August because of their dependence on seasonal floods, which inundate the Gangetic

floodplain areas essentially needed for reproduction and feeding. The monthly data of rainfall from the middle stretch of the river at Allahabad from 1979-2009 revealed that the percentage of total rainfall in the peak breeding period (May-August) declined by 7% whereas it increased by 4% in the post- breeding period when resorption of eggs of Indian Major Carps set in. This shift and decrease in the rainfall pattern resulting in the alteration of the required flow and turbidity during breeding season is a major factor responsible for failure in breeding and consequent recruitment of young ones of Indian major carps in the river Ganga. An adequate flood level during the monsoon months (June-September) is required in the river Ganges for inundating the floodplains where majority of the Gangetic carps breed (Vass et al. 2009; Das et al. 2013) (Figure 1).

4.2 Breeding of fish in aquaculture farms in West Bengal and Orissa

Extended breeding period - The aquaculture hatcheries in the states of West Bengal and Orissa extensively breed the Indian major carps (IMC) *C. catla*, *L. rohita* and *C. mrigala* which form the mainstay of Inland aquaculture in the country. These fishes are breed in captivity by the technique of hypophysation during the monsoon season (June-September). In recent decade the phenomenon of IMC maturing and spawning as early as March is observed. The average minimum and maximum temperature throughout the state has increased and rainfall pattern has changed. Analysis of the air temperature data (1999-2009) recorded by IIMT Pune (2005), during the maturing and breeding months of Indian fishes carps ie., (January-April and May-September) from two districts North 24 Parganas and Bankura, West Bengal in the gangetic plains of India where aquaculture hatchery farms are located indicate that the mean maximum

and the mean minimum air temperature and the mean minimum water temperature has increased and higher temperature is witnessed during colder months (Figure 2). Data collected from the hatcheries indicate that during 1980 the breeding of IMCs started during the last week of May, whereas during recent years 2005-2008 breeding programmes in the hatcheries were initiated during mid April. As a result, an extended breeding period of IMCs by 40-60 days with breeding season extending from 110-120 days (Pre1980-85) to 160-165 days (2000-2008) is evident in fifty fish seed hatcheries in four districts of West Bengal,

India viz. North 24 Parganas, Bankura. This is in agreement to our previous findings (Dey et al. 2007). Temperature is one of the important factors influencing the reproductive cycle in fishes. This climatic factor along with rainfall and photoperiod stimulate the endocrine glands which help in the maturation of the gonads of Indian major carp.

The aquaculture hatcheries in Orissa the breeding period of IMCs in the hatcheries has advanced by over 60 to 75 days during the last decade (Das et al. 2012).

Fig. 2 Relationship between GSI and water temperature (Reproduced from Brandt and Kirsch 1993)

4.3 Geographic distribution of fish in river Ganga

Warm water fish species - *Glossogobius giuris*, *Puntius ticto*, *Xenentodon cancila* and *Mystus vittatus* that were available earlier only in the middle stretch of the river Ganga are now available in the colder stretch of the river around Haridwar. Thus, a perceptible shift in geographic distribution of the fishes of river Ganga has occurred in the upper colder stretch of river Ganga. At Haridwar during the period 1980-2009 the minimum water temperature increased by 0.99 °C as a result the stretch of river Ganga around Haridwar has become a more congenial habitat for warm water fishes (Vass et al. 2009; Das 2013).

4.4 Aquatic habitat availability and fish species richness

Analysis of time series data (1994-2009) of climate variables and its impact on fish species richness in 14 major rivers of the India revealed that the most influential determinants of species richness were the factors such as: surface area of the river basin (0.439) followed by fish habitat availability potential (0.326) a synthesis of the variables rainfall, discharge and sediment load. The predicted loss of fish species is evident at a 10% alteration in the ecological variables of the rivers in most of the rivers and can

be very useful for planners and conservationists. (Das et al. 2011).

4.5 Impact on biodiversity

Climate change elements could synergistically affect fish habitat alterations. Habitat availability for fish and associated organisms might increase or decrease. This would affect fish at the primary, secondary and tertiary levels of biological organization.

4.5.1 Alteration in phytoplankton species in river Ganga

In last 20 years, about 42 - 44 genera of phytoplankton have been disappeared from the river Ganga. The contribution of some genera like Amphicampus, Tetracycles, Diatoma and Ceratoneus have become insignificant. Certain genera such as Tetracycles and Amphycampus are usually found in cold mountainous regions, likewise the genera Diatoma and Ceratoneus are often encountered in cool temperate regions than in warmer areas. Here during the last decade's environmental changes due to rise in water temperature resulted in depletion of the stenothermal phytoplankton genera mentioned above.(Vass et al. 2009).

4.5.2 Salinity induced alteration in fish composition

In Krishna estuary the water availability in the river downstream of Prakasam Barrage has dwindled. As a result an increase in salinity below the barrage from 20 to 35 ppt has occurred because of tidal seawater incursion into the riverine stretch and mullets are the dominant catches (80 %). On the contrary there has been an overall decline in the salinity of Hooghly-Matla estuary with gradient and marine zones pushed down towards sea. This has brought about distinct change in the species composition of fishes with freshwater species making their appearance in tidal zone and a few neritic species disappearing. (Das et al. 2010).

4.5.3 Invasion of exotic fish species

In the Allahabad and Varanasi stretch of river Ganga, the share of exotics is mostly that of common carp and is approximately 15 to 30 % of the total catch. In Yamuna (Agra and Mathura) stretch *C. carpio*, *O. niloticus* and *C. garipeniensis* constitutes approx. 18-25% of the catch (Das et al. 2013).

4.5.4 Alteration in fish species richness in Indian rivers

Time series data 1994–2009 analysis of 7 climate related variables of 14 major rivers of India indicated that species richness were i) Surface area of the river basin (0.439) followed by fish habitat availability potential (0.326) a synthesis of the variables rainfall, Discharge and sediment load. The predicted loss of fish species is evident at a 10% alteration in the ecological variables of the rivers in most of the rivers (Das et al. 2011).

5. Impact on marine fish and associated organisms

The alterations in the climatic factors over the years in the Indian marine environment elicited perceptible responses in fish and associated marine organism as detailed by Vivekanandan et al. (2010).

5.1 Changes in species composition of phytoplankton

Zooplankton, especially the copepods, are regarded to act as sentinels to the marine biogeochemical cycles. During 1998 to 2005, a decrease in the abundance of copepods was observed during SW monsoon in the Arabian Sea. Significant changes in the community structure of copepods in active upwelling waters along the southwest coast were also observed. This is significant because the abundance of zooplankton which serves as food for many pelagic fishes in the sea determines the larval recruitment as well as the abundance of some adult fishes like the Indian mackerel.

5.2 Extension of distributional boundary of small pelagic fishes

Small pelagic fishes, the oil sardine *Sardinella longiceps* and the Indian mackerel *Rastrelliger kanagurta* are a cheap source of protein, providing sustenance and nutritional food for millions of coastal people. Until 1985, almost the entire catch of oil sardine was from the Malabar upwelling zone (between latitude 8°N and 14°N and longitude 75°E and 77°E with annual average sea surface temperature ranges from 27 to 29°C) and the catch was either very low or there was no catch from latitudes north of 14°N. In the last two decades, however, the catches from latitude 14°N - 20°N are increasing, contributing about 15% to the all-India oil sardine catch during 2006. The surface waters of the Indian seas are warming by 0.04°C per decade, and the warmer tongue (27-28.5°C) of the surface waters is expanding to latitudes north of 14°N, enabling the oil sardine and Indian mackerel to extend their distributional range to northern latitudes. It is also found that the catches from the Malabar upwelling zone has not decreased indicating the distributional “extension” and not distributional “shift”. The Indian mackerel are also found to extend the distribution to the northern latitudes of the Indian seas in a similar way.

6. Impact on fish

6.1 Spawning behaviour of anadromous fishes (*T. ilisha*)

Studies conducted in the anadromous species *T. ilisha* in river Hooghly through regression analysis of GSI with water temperature indicated that the GSI attained two peaks at 29°C and 32°C respectively. Patterns of different stages of maturity in relation to water temperature indicated that VIIth stage of maturity attained peak in the water temperature range between 30°C and 31°C (Figure 3). These two findings indicated that temperature range between 29°C and 32°C could be conducive for spawning. Forecast temperature based on time series data could be plugged into a model for predicting GSI for increased or decreased temperature. Earlier studies reported optimal temperature range of 26°C to 30°C for spawning of *T. ilisha*. However the present study indicates favourable spawning temperature range up to 32°C. Temperature may be a controlling factor in determining the timing of development and migration (Sharma et al. 2014)

6.2 Effect on fish growth

Alteration in water temperature influences on the metabolism, feed consumption, growth, habitat selection, foraging, and predator-prey interaction. The growth rate potential of fish provides a good measure of habitat quality (Tyler and Brandt 2001) and effectively incorporates biotic and abiotic characteristics of the environment in a metric that directly relates to the fitness of fish (Brandt and Kirsch 1993).

In a climate warming scenario the volume of thermal habitat for the fish will undergo changes. If the volume is large and if the same number of prey is distributed across this volume of habitat, prey densities encountered by a predator would be reduced. Reduced prey densities would reduce the predator encounter rate with prey, which would reduce predator consumption rate (Das et al. 2013).

Assessment of the impact of unit rise in temperature on the growth of *Labeo rohita* fingerlings revealed that the carp reared at 34°C grew significantly faster (18.38 cg in a day) than those at 29-33°C and 35°C. It would take average 54-55

days for a carp to double in weight at 30°C to 33°C and 35°C, but at 34 °C it would take only 35-36 days (Das et al. 2013).

Fig. 3 Relationship between maturity stages and water temperature (Reproduced from Brandt and Kirsch 1993)

6.3 Fish health

Temperature fluctuation- Fluctuating temperature very often disturb the homeostasis of fish and subject them to physiological stress and shift in habitat or mortality. Fishes are often subjected to the hazards of rapid temperature changes in tropical waters for various reasons. Investigation on the alteration occurring in the levels of various stress sensitive blood and tissue parameters of the fish *Labeo rohita* and *Rita rita* acclimatized at 29°C and subjected to a rapid sublethal rise to 35°C and then maintained at this temperature indicated that the homeostatic mechanism of the fish was stressed (Das et al. 2002). The changes evident were hypercholesterolemia indicating impaired sterol mechanism, hyperglycemia and decreased blood sugar regulatory mechanism. Pituitary activation as evidenced by interrenal ascorbic acid depletion and cortisol elevation was pronounced. Oxygen consumption in both the fishes increased as judged by increased haemoglobin. Simultaneously it was observed that compensatory responses were initiated in the fishes within 72 hrs as adaptation to the stress of elevated temperature. But if the stress of enhanced temperature is of chronic nature as in a climate warming scenario then the tolerance limits of fishes may be exceeded.

At present *Labeo rohita* seems to be acclimated to cold water aquaculture. Records show that Indian major carps cannot withstand water temperature below 10°C and does not grow at all if temperature is below 16°C. The climate changes are now evident from the ongoing farming practices in the Uttarakhand hills (1200-1600msl) where Indian major carps, particularly *Labeo rohita* is thriving well in the pond conditions at Pati, Champawat district, where it could not survive in trials made 10-15 years back probably due to low

temperature. This can be attributed to decrease in frost duration in the region and resultant increase of 1.0-1.5°C water temperature. This indicates that the increased water temperature might support culture of Indian major carps in the upland regions in coming years. But at the same time this would be an alarming signal for existence of valuable trout fishery (Sharma et al. 2014, NICRA Annual Report 2012)

6.4 Impact of water scarcity

The impact of deficient rainfall and high temperature during drought period of 2009 was assessed on the fish seed hatcheries in two districts Bankura and 24 Parganas (N) of West Bengal (Das et al. 2011). These two districts have the capacity to produce 5604 to 13400 million spawn in a year (DFAARFH 2009). The drought conditions in 2009 affected 92% of the fish seed hatcheries in the districts.

The fish seed production in the district North 24 came down from 4532 million during 2008 to 4368 million spawn during 2009 (DFAARFH 2009). The production in the hatcheries of Bankura was stable with some hatcheries forced to cease fish breeding fish for 20-25 days as there was no buyers.

During the drought the demand and sell price of fish seed came down drastically. As a result of scarcity of rainfall the nurseries and rearing ponds either had very little water level or were dried up completely rendering them unsuitable to stock the fish seed. During previous years 1999-2008 the price of fish seed during the months March-April was Rs. 600/bati which came down to Rs. 450-500/bati during 2009. During other season the price per (bati) ranged between Rs.220-250 previously but came down to Rs.100-120 per bati during 2009 as there were few takers (Das et al. 2011).

6.5 Potential Impact of cyclones

Tropical cyclones are major hazards in tropical coastal regions, both in terms of loss of life and economic damage. Such cyclones originate in the Bay of Bengal during the spring (April-May) and fall (October- November) inter-monsoon. They are predicted to increase in frequency.

These cyclones with tremendous speed hit the coastline and inundate the shores with strong tidal wave, severely destroying and disturbing coastal resources. The intrusion of seawater into the upstream riverine zone through estuaries, creeks and inlets has high probability to alter the chemical composition of the inland waters.

Digital Elevation Model generated for the coastal areas of South 24 Parganas district showed that during cyclones at a sea level rise of 1m, 3% land area and at 2m rise in sea level 11% of land area of the district respectively will be submerged. Thus 11% land area constituting agricultural fields and aquaculture pond is highly vulnerable to the extreme events of cyclones and storms in the district (Das et al. 2013).

7. Vulnerability assessment

The greatest limitation towards developing an effective adaptation strategy for climate change in India is the lack of vulnerability assessment framework and vulnerability mapping of various climate sensitive sectors of Indian economy. In the absence of such quantified data implementing adaptation measures is difficult.

The first significant contribution towards development of vulnerability index and vulnerability mapping of the inland aquatic resources and fisheries to climate variability

was conducted in 14 districts of the highest fish and fish seed producing state in India, West Bengal by Central Inland Fisheries Research Institute.

The study developed a vulnerability assessment framework using selected indices of climate exposure, sensitivity and adaptive capacity relevant to inland fisheries (Das et al. 2016) (Figure 4). Application of this framework showed that the differential vulnerability of inland fisheries to climate variability exhibited among the districts of West Bengal reflected different spatial combinations of climate exposure, sensitivity and adaptive capacity. The low adaptation capacity of people of Nadia, Mursidabad, East Medinipur, Howrah and Malda ranked the districts most vulnerable though moderately exposed to climate variability. Whereas, the cyclone risk coastal districts of North 24 Parganas and South 24 Parganas were less vulnerable. The relative low vulnerability scores of sensitivity components in these districts moderated their vulnerability. However, these two districts were highly vulnerable when exposed to extreme climatic conditions as evident in these districts during the devastation caused by cyclone Aila in 2009. The low adaptive capacity of the fishers in the districts limited their capacity to cope up with the extensive loss to fish production and infrastructural facility associated with such extreme climate conditions. The low adaptive capacity of the fishers was related to the homogenous livelihood pattern, less opportunity to diversify the livelihood sources and decreasing availability of natural aquatic resources. Thus the research provides a practical analytical tool to understand the contribution of the indices of the sector to climate vulnerability at district level and forms an important basis for policy makers to develop appropriate adaptation strategies to minimize the risk of fisheries sector.

Fig. 4 Construction of vulnerability Index Reproduced from FAO (2014)

8. Adaptation Options for Inland Fisheries in India

8.1 Enhanced water temperature

In the fish culture system enhanced water temperature will decrease the dissolved oxygen content in water. Water holds less oxygen at higher temperature as such fish requires more oxygen as temperature rises. Increased growth and food conversion and enhanced breeding period in hatcheries will occur along with increased disease incidence. Operationally there will be changes in the level of production with increase in the fish production cost.

Adaptation Options- The IMCs maintain their normal metabolic activities upto 34°C. Beyond this temperature growth and food conversion are affected (FAO 2011). Under such condition, substitution of Indian major carps with low oxygen tolerant species like catfishes in the culture system would be advantageous.

8.2 Floods

Flood damages fish culture facilities, loss of fish stock and introduction of fish predators and pathogens. Operational cost of the facilities will also increase.

Adaptations options- To offset the loss of fish due to recurrent floods, provision for continuous supply of seed from fish hatcheries is required. Management practice should emphasize harvesting of fish at smaller size and selection of fish species that require short culture period with minimum expenditure on inputs.

8.3 Drought

The impact on the culture system will reflect in reduced water quality and limitation in the cultivable water area and volume. As a result there will be loss in fish production.

Adaptation options- Smaller ponds that retain water for 2-4 months can be used for fish production with fish species like catfish and appropriate management practices.

8.4 Cyclones and storms

Inundation, flooding and salinity changes occur in the fish culture facilities resulting in the loss of fish/prawn stock and introduction of predators. Operational damage to the facilities may lead to financial loss.

Adaptation options- An early warning system of weather events is essential to cope up with post cyclone management. It is essential to optimally utilize the normal culture periods and maximize fish production and profit by selecting suitable fish species and appropriate cultural practices.

8.5 Water stress

In the coming years, water stress may manifest itself by decrease in water availability both in terms of quality and quantity. This will result in reduced production capacity and increased cost of maintaining pond level artificially. Wetland systems are highly vulnerable to changes in quantity and

quality of their water supply and alterations in hydrological regimes. Climate change is expected to reduce the number of functioning wetlands and their functional capacity within most ecoregions and will lead to shift in geographic location of certain types of wetlands.

Adaptation options- Integrated farming is suitable under water stress conditions as it not only recycles nutrients but also increases the use of water and energy many folds. Under such conditions short duration crops (1-4months) of fish and prawn are recommended in small seasonal type ponds. Wetland restoration should be realized on a regional and mega-watershed level, after examination of habitat response to climatic variables. It will be judicious to introduce climate resilient development strategies that both support general development and climate adaptation in the vulnerable region. Strategies such as de-silting of wetlands, opening and widening of linkage channels, prevention or reduction of additional, maintaining hydrology, reducing pollution, controlling exotic vegetation, and protecting wetland biological diversity and integrity are important.

9. Research gaps and future directions

An important question that this paper aims to address is: given our current knowledge, what will happen to inland fisheries in India under on-going climate change scenario? There is strong evidence suggesting that climate change will alter the distribution and productivity of resources that are available in India, affecting the economics of the inland fisheries industry and associated sectors. Interactions between climate change and other human disturbances render detection and attribution of climate change effects on fisheries difficult.

To improve our ability to project the implications of climate change for inland fisheries in India, key biophysical, social and economic knowledge gaps need to be addressed. Climatic models need to be developed and improved at regional and sub-regional scales coupling them with physical and biogeochemical dynamics anticipated in our inland waters in response to the climate change. In this context here is a need to develop better understanding of the links between projected climate change, environmental responses, fish stock and aquatic ecosystem responses. Research with regard to evolutionary behaviour and adaptation of species to climate change and its effect on food web structure in the inland waters will provide better understanding of changes in biodiversity in climate change scenario. Appropriate intervention of research programmes are required for appropriate methodology for vulnerability assessment by improving parameterisation of 'risk exposure', sensitivity and adaptive capacity based on long time historical data. On stakeholders side studies on impact of climate change and human activity on their socioeconomic conditions are essential for effective adaptation and mitigation options to be developed. It is also important to understand how different fishery sectors may respond to proposed mitigation and adaptation measures. Addressing these knowledge gaps will clearly require both within-discipline studies and interdisciplinary efforts.

It is important to develop adaptation policies for the fishing sector, which could be updated and adapted as new

knowledge emerges. Anthropogenic impacts on inland aquatic ecosystems through overfishing, habitat destruction, pollution, etc. reduce adaptive capacity of the ecosystems and organisms to climate and other environmental changes. Reduction in human pressure on ecosystem will thus ensure higher resilience and adaptive capacity to climate change. Improving education and communication within the fishing industry about climate change could be important for effective implementation of climate change mitigation and adaptation policies. Such measures would allow the fisheries industry to develop capacity and to respond effectively to threats or opportunities posed by climate change.

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